

The Impact of Employment Transition on Self-reported Health in Russia (2015–2022)

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Abstract

The relationship between labor market status and individual health has been a central topic in academic research for decades. The findings remain inconclusive despite extensive studies, largely due to variations in national contexts, study periods, and health indicators used. This study focuses on Russia and examines the direct causal effect of employment status on self-reported health outcomes.

We employ a quasi-experimental Difference-in-Differences (DID) approach to address potential biases arising from self-selection and indirect selection (confounding). Our analysis is based on data from waves 24–31 (2015–2022) of the Russian Longitudinal Monitoring Survey – Higher School of Economics (RLMS-HSE), a nationally representative panel dataset.

The results confirm a significant causal relationship between employment status and self-reported health. However, the analysis does not conclusively confirm or reject the hypothesized negative impact of unemployment on health outcomes in the Russian population, highlighting the need for further investigation. Moreover, the extended analysis reveals a significant positive association of higher education levels with self-reported health, while being divorced is associated with a negative impact on health outcomes. Additionally, we run synthetic DID models to demonstrate that our results are robust to changes in specifications.

Our findings have important policy implications, providing a strong foundation for developing initiatives focused on expanding employment opportunities, ultimately contributing to improved population health. In Russia, where healthcare costs are state-funded, these measures can enhance population health and reduce long-term government healthcare expenditures.

Keywords

difference-in-difference, employment transition, Russia, self-reported health, unemployment

JEL codes: C21, I10, I12

Introduction

The relationship between labor market status and individual health has been a central focus of the literature for many years, yet findings across studies remain inconclusive. While the existence of this relationship is empirically supported by the vast majority of studies, its direction remains a subject of debate (Picchio and Ubaldi 2024).

The literature identifies two primary pathways of influence: direct and reverse. The causal (direct) relationship, also referred to as social causation, posits that transitioning to unemployment adversely affects individuals' physical and mental health. This negative effect is explained by both manifest and latent deprivation, as outlined by Jahoda (1982). Manifest deprivation refers to the loss of financial resources necessary to maintain a proper standard of living. As individuals rely on their savings and experience a decline in income, they may find it challenging to afford a nutritious diet, regular exercise, timely medical care, and other essential services. In addition, losing their jobs deprives individuals of latent benefits, which include time structure, social contact, a sense of collective purpose (i.e., feeling useful to others), status, and regular activity (Jahoda 1982). Consequently, unemployment can undermine overall well-being, which may be reflected in self-reported health (SRH).

Reverse causality suggests that an individuals' health status can influence their employment status. This relationship is explained by the (self-) selection hypothesis, which posits that poor health may be a significant factor in job loss and challenges in re-employment. Individuals with poor health tend to be less productive, less reliable, and have higher absenteeism, increasing their risk of being selected for unemployment (Junna et al. 2022).

An additional third explanation for the relationship between health and employment status is indirect selection or confounding effect, where common factors contribute to poor health and unemployment. For instance, empirical evidence suggests a positive relationship between education and health (Conti et al. 2010). At the same time, individuals with lower levels of education face a higher risk of becoming unemployed.

It is important to note that direct and reverse relationships are not mutually exclusive (Krug and Eberl 2018). The influence of each direction depends on and is reinforced by the other (Bartley et al. 2006). Thus, assessing each causal direction's influence in isolation becomes essential. Most empirical studies in this area rely on cross-sectional data analysis, which does not permit a clear distinction between these effects. Consequently, the estimated coefficients in such studies capture a combination of both direct and reverse causality.

The (self-)selection bias can be mitigated through longitudinal model analysis. Researchers apply various methods, including lagged health indicators (Johansson et al. 2020; Stauder 2019), Heckman selection models (Mercurieva 2004), instrumental variables (Gathergood 2013), natural experiments (Schmitz 2011), and the generalized method of moments (GMM) (Arellano and Bond 1991; Krug and Eberl 2018). There are also quasi-experimental approaches that enable evaluation by establishing treatment and control groups using the observational studies data. Notably, approaches such as propensity score matching (Böckerman and Ilmakunnas 2009; Ronchetti and Terriau 2019; Lazareva 2020; Kaneva 2024) and difference-in-differences (DID) (Gebel and Voßmer 2014; Lazareva 2020) are widely employed to assess causal relationships between health and employment. The findings of these studies demonstrate that the impact of employment and unemployment on health is heterogeneous, varying by health type (physical or psychological), country, demographic factors, and the study period. For instance, evidence from Finland (Johansson et al. 2020) and Russia (Lazareva 2020; Kaneva 2024) indicates a decline in SRH following the transi-

tion to unemployment. Conversely, studies from Finland, France, and Germany suggest that SRH remains unaffected by unemployment (Böckerman and Ilmakunnas 2009; Gebel and Voßemer 2014; Ronchetti and Terriau 2019). Stauder's (2019) research on the relationship between unemployment and health in Germany reveals that while physical health deterioration due to unemployment does not occur immediately, it gains momentum over time, with the effect being more pronounced among older individuals. Other studies establish a causal relationship between employment status and mental health (Galić and Šverko 2008; Gatherhood 2013; Gebel and Voßemer 2014). Additionally, Shuring's et al. (2011) findings confirm the positive impact of re-employment on various dimensions of health, including physical functioning, social activity, vitality, and mental health. We define "re-employment" as gaining employment after an un-employment spell. We use the term "re-employment" to highlight the meaning of employment transition.

While extensive research exists for European countries, only a few studies explore the relationship between labor market status and self-reported health in Russia. Nazarova (2004) finds that better health is associated with a higher likelihood of having part-time jobs in addition to primary employment. Better health is also a significant factor in deciding to initiate a job search (Furmanov and Chernysheva 2012). Pensioners in good health are more likely to land a job or to be economically active (Mercurieva 2004). The employment rate among women in Russia is higher for females who report good or very good health (Karabchuk and Nagernyak 2013). Few studies on Russia isolate direct causality (one exception is Lazareva (2020) which presents matching and DID estimators for the analysis of labor market shock on health), and we have not found any research assessing re-employment's impact on health (for a more detailed review, see Kaneva 2024; Kaneva and Moiseenko 2024). This underscores the need for further investigation in this context.

Our study fills the gap in the research on the relationship between labor market status and health in Russia. It aims to evaluate the *causal impact* of transitioning to unemployment or employment status on individuals' self-reported health (SRH) in Russia while accounting for self-selection bias. To accomplish this, we apply the difference-in-differences (DID) method.

The study tests two hypotheses:

H1: Transitioning from employment or economic inactivity to unemployment results in poorer health outcomes.

H2: Re-employment after unemployment or economic inactivity positively influences individual health.

Methodology

The difference-in-differences (DID) design is the oldest and most widely used quasi-experimental research approach for estimating causal effects, with origins tracing back to Snow's analysis of a cholera outbreak in London in 1855 (Cunningham 2021).

Canonical DID estimates the average treatment effect on the treated (ATT) using two differences: the difference between two time periods (before (t) and after the treatment period ($t + 1$)) and the difference between two groups (treatment group and control group). By estimating differences across two periods – subtracting the pre-treatment outcome from the post-treatment outcome – the method removes group-invariant time trends or time-invariant level differences between groups (confounding effects), thereby isolating the causal effect of the treatment (Zeldow and Hatfield 2021).

We use the traditional DID approach, controlling for individual fixed effects. Detailed explanation of the DID methodology is presented in Kotyrlo (2024).

To test Hypothesis 1, we define the treatment as a transition from employment (or economic inactivity) to unemployment, with the outcome variable being individual health status (*SRH*). The treatment group consists of individuals who were either employed or economically inactive in the year t and subsequently transitioned to unemployment in the year $t + 1$. The control group includes individuals who remained employed throughout the entire analysis period ($t + 1$ years).

In Hypothesis 2, we define the treatment as gaining employment after a period of unemployment or economic inactivity. The treatment group includes individuals who were workless in years t (classified as either unemployed or economically inactive) and became employed in year $t + 1$. The control group consists of individuals who never became employed during the entire analyzed period ($t + 1$ years). Typically, pensioners and students are excluded when constructing a sample in labor market research. However, their exclusion in our case resulted in an insufficient number of respondents in the experimental group. To ensure sufficient sample size, we included employed individuals, the unemployed, those not working and not looking for work, as well as pensioners, students, and homemakers.

The causal effect of unemployment transition (or average treatment effect on treated, ATT) is equal to the coefficient β_3 in the following OLS regression:

$$SRH_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Treated_i + \beta_2 Post_t + \beta_3 Post_t \times Treated_i + \beta_4 Controls_{it} + \theta_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where *SRH* is self-reported health. *Treated* is a dummy variable that takes the value of 1 for the treatment group (individuals who experienced a change in employment status) and 0 for the control group (those who did not experience this change). *Post* is a time dummy variable, set to 1 for the post-treatment period and 0 for the pre-treatment period. $Post_t \times Treated_i$ is the interaction between group and period. This is the key variable that captures the effect of the intervention on the experimental group (i.e., ATT), as it equals 1 only for the experimental group ($Treated_i = 1$) in the post-intervention period ($Post_t = 1$). To control for unobserved heterogeneity, individual fixed effects θ_i were included in the equation.

The basic regression model includes three variables ($Treated_i$, $Post_t$, and $Post_t \times Treated_i$) while the extended model incorporates an additional set of control variables that also affect both health outcomes and labor market status, represented by the vector $Controls_{it}$. We assume that gender, age, education, and marital status influence labor market status in Russia. In addition, we propose that finding a job in a city or town is easier than doing that in the rural areas or urban-type settlements. Therefore, our model’s control variables include gender, age, age squared (Toge and Blekesaune 2015; Draydakakis 2015), marital status, education level, and living in a town or regional center.

After estimating the ATT using a traditional DID, we further assess the robustness of our results by applying the Synthetic Difference-in-Differences (SDID) method.

The SDID estimator, recently proposed by Arkhangelsky et al. (2021), combines features of both DID and the synthetic control method. It improves the credibility of causal inference when the parallel trends assumption may be questionable or when treatment and control groups differ substantially. Specifically, SDID constructs synthetic control weights to better balance the pre-treatment outcomes between treated and control units. To improve balance, unit weights $\hat{\omega}_i^{sdid}$ that align pre-treatment trends in self-reported health (*SRH*) between treated and control units are introduced. SDID also estimates time weights $\hat{\lambda}_t^{sdid}$, giving

more importance to pre-treatment periods that closely resemble the post-treatment period in terms of outcome dynamics.

Hence, the formula for ATT estimation in SDID can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\hat{\tau}_{sdid}, \hat{\mu}, \hat{\alpha}_i, \hat{\beta}_t) = \\ & \arg \min_{\tau, \mu, \alpha, \beta} \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{t=1}^T (SRH_{it} - \mu - \alpha_i - \beta_t - W_{it} \tau)^2 \hat{\omega}_i^{sdid} \hat{\lambda}_t^{sdid} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where μ denotes the intercept, while α_i and β_t represent individual and time fixed effects, respectively. W_{it} is treatment indicator, defined as the interaction between a group indicator (*Treated_i*) and a time indicator (*Post_t*). The coefficient τ captures ATT, which is the parameter of interest.

Notably, the SDID method requires a balanced panel without missing observations; thus, units with incomplete outcome data across the panel period are excluded from the analysis.

We use STATA 17 for all statistical analysis.

Data

We use waves 24-31 (2015-2022) of the Russia Longitudinal Monitoring Survey – Higher School of Economics population survey (RLMS), yielding a nationally representative population sample from a repeated cross-section survey conducted each autumn. The survey is based on the principle of “repeated sampling of dwellings,” in which all household members are interviewed each year (if they can be contacted within three visits), and then the dwelling itself (rather than the household) is followed. The survey collects data across a rich range of the population’s socioeconomic, demographic, and health characteristics. The sample was constrained to the adult working-age population – persons older than 18 and younger than 55 for women and 60 for men.

We choose 2015–2022 as our study period to ensure a sufficient number of time points for reliable estimation. As noted by Angrist and Pischke (2015, p. 188), the difference-in-differences model performs best with four or more data points. In addition, we vary the study window by shortening the pre-treatment period to test the sensitivity of our results to different lengths of labor market stability before the transition occurs.

The self-reported health variable is based on how people assess their health and is a categorical variable ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 corresponds to “very bad health” and 5 to “very good health”. We construct the variable of interest – being unemployed – from question J90 “primary occupation.” An individual is recorded as unemployed if he answers yes to the statement – “temporarily not employed for other reasons and looking for a job.” We also created the variables “working,” “retired,” and “outside the labor force (economically inactive).” The latter category includes carers, students, and those unemployed for health reasons. If an individual agrees to the statement “temporarily not employed for other reasons and not looking for a job,” he is also considered economically inactive.

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics for the variables used in the analysis for 2015-2022. We provide statistics for the full sample since our research spans multiple models. Our sample is 49% male, 66% are married, 30% attained tertiary education. 69% of respondents reside in regional centers and towns. 18% of individuals were unemployed for at least one year during the study period. This sample is further used to define treatment and control groups for various periods.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics for the Variables Used in the Analysis, 2015–2022

Variable	Observations	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Self-reported health	79500	3.391	0.631	1	5
Being unemployed for at least one period	79682	0.177	0.381	0	1
Being employed for at least one period	79682	0.848	0.358	0	1
Male	80044	0.488	0.500	0	1
Age	80044	37.191	11.529	16	60
Age squared/100	80044	15.161	8.676	2.56	36.00
Married*	79949	0.662	0.473	0	1
Divorced	79949	0.082	0.274	0	1
Widowed	79949	0.020	0.140	0	1
Single	79949	0.236	0.425	0	1
Basic education*	79993	0.003	0.056	0	1
Incomplete secondary	79993	0.142	0.349	0	1
Secondary	79993	0.302	0.459	0	1
Vocational	79993	0.255	0.436	0	1
Tertiary	79993	0.299	0.458	0	1
Town/city	80044	0.687	0.464	0	1

Note: *denotes reference category. Source: calculated from the RLMS dataset

Results

Both hypotheses were tested using the DID method across six distinct periods: 2015–2022, 2018–2022, 2019–2022, 2015–2021, 2016–2021, and 2017–2021. For each hypothesis, corresponding treatment and control groups were established, with the number of respondents in each group presented in Table 2. Consistent with the research design described above, individuals included in the analysis were required to remain in the same labor market status throughout the entire pre-transition period and to experience a single, clearly defined transition in the final year of the observation window. Across all periods, the treatment group is considerably smaller than the control group for both hypotheses. The disparity is particularly notable for Hypothesis 1, where the control group consistently comprises thousands of respondents, while the treatment group remains relatively limited in size. For periods spanning more years, the number of respondents is smaller because fewer individuals experience prolonged unemployment (e.g., 5 or 6 years) before becoming employed. Conversely, it is also less common for individuals to remain employed or economically inactive for an extended period before transitioning to unemployment.

To test the hypothesis, we employed both basic and extended traditional OLS DID models, incorporating individual fixed effects to control for unobserved heterogeneity. Table 3 presents the estimated ATT. When testing Hypothesis 1, the results were not statistically

significant, and the assumption of parallel trends was not confirmed. This indicates that the negative impact of unemployment on health in Russia has neither been confirmed nor rejected. Several factors may contribute to this outcome, including an expanded sample comprising groups such as pensioners and students, which are often excluded from similar studies but could not be excluded here in order to retain a sufficient number of respondents. Furthermore, the substantial imbalance in the number of respondents between the control and treatment groups, as highlighted in Table 2, could have influenced the findings.

Table 2. Distribution of respondents across treatment and control groups for each time period

Periods	Hypothesis 1		Hypothesis 2	
	Treatment group	Control group	Treatment group	Control group
2015-2022	44	3542	45	282
2018-2022	85	5237	145	616
2019-2022	106	5898	219	616
2015-2021	52	4088	91	406
2016-2021	67	4728	122	538
2017-2021	93	5554	162	708

Table 3. Estimated ATT (beta 3) Using Basic and Extended OLS Models with Individual Fixed Effects

Periods	2015- 2022	2018- 2022	2019- 2022	2015- 2021	2016- 2021	2017- 2021
Hypothesis 1: The causal effect of transitioning to unemployment on SRH						
Basic model	-0.038 (0.069)	-0.011 (0.054)	-0.010 (0.049)	0.049 (0.073)	0.044 (0.067)	0.056 (0.054)
Control for individual fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Extended model	-0.042 (0.069)	-0.008 (0.054)	-0.012 (0.049)	0.044 (0.073)	0.040 (0.067)	0.052 (0.054)
Control for individual fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Hypothesis 2: The causal effect of transitioning to employment on SRH						
Basic model	0.006 (0.070)	-0.043 (0.042)	-0.023 (0.035)	0.174*** (0.064)	0.154*** (0.053)	0.142*** (0.045)
Control for individual fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Extended model	0.018 (0.069)	-0.042 (0.043)	-0.032 (0.035)	0.187*** (0.065)	0.159*** (0.054)	0.129*** (0.046)
Control for individual fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

For Hypothesis 2, statistically significant results were obtained across three periods, including 2021 (2015–2021, 2016–2021, 2017–2021), with coefficients ranging from 0.129 to 0.187. The parallel trend assumption is tested graphically (Fig. 1). The results confirm it only for the two periods, 2016–2021 and 2017–2021 (panels b and c). The graphs illustrate that, at the start of these periods, SRH was higher for the treatment group, with the trends for both groups moving nearly parallel throughout the period (not perfectly, but sufficiently close). The estimation results from the basic and extended DID OLS models with covariates for the 2016–2021 period indicate that transitioning to employment increases SRH by approximately 0.154 and 0.159, respectively. Comparable findings were observed for the 2017–2021 period, with coefficients of 0.142 and 0.129 for the basic and extended models, respectively. While the coefficients for the 2015–2021 period are somewhat higher (0.174 and 0.187), the parallel trend assumption was not satisfied for this timeframe. Overall, these results provide evidence supporting Hypothesis 2, suggesting that gaining employment in Russia has a positive impact on individuals' health.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the parallel trend assumption Hypothesis 2. *Note:* A. 2015–2021, B. 2016–2021, and C. 2017–2021. Abbreviations: SRH = self-reported health. The solid and dashed lines represent the average SRH of the treatment and control groups, respectively, for each year over the period; the graph for the period 2015–2021 does not satisfy the parallel trend assumption, while the graphs for 2016–2021 and 2017–2021 confirm it.

Let us consider the results of the extended DID models for the periods 2015–2021, 2016–2021, and 2017–2021 under Hypothesis 1. For these periods, the ATT estimation using DID OLS with individual fixed effects showed that none of the control variables were statistically significant.

Notably, when individual fixed effects were not included in the model, several control variables – particularly education level and marital status – showed significant associations with self-reported health. The results of the extended models for Hypothesis 2 (Table 4) indicate a statistically significant positive association between education and health. Having a university degree is associated with a 0.66-unit increase in SRH (ranging from 1 to 5) compared with those with basic education. Within our linear model, we can't claim causality between education and health, as earlier studies have found endogeneity between these variables due to reverse causality (for a detailed analysis, please see Kosorukova et al. 2025). Additionally, there is a negative, statistically significant association between being divorced and SRH. These associations are generally consistent with one another and are statistically significant across the three periods analyzed. The estimated treatment effects in these models are close to those obtained in the fixed-effects specifications and remain statistically significant at the 5% level, thereby supporting Hypothesis 2.

When we include individual fixed effects in the models presented in Table 4, several independent variables become insignificant; however, age, sex and town/regional center retain their significance across specifications. The extended model confirms Hypothesis 2.

As a robustness check, we estimated the ATT using the SDID method for three periods: 2015–2021, 2016–2021, and 2017–2021. The results are presented in Table 5. Across the three examined periods (2015–2021, 2016–2021, and 2017–2021), the estimated ATT using the SDID method remained highly consistent at approximately 0.177–0.178 and statistically significant at the 1% level. An additional specification of the SDID model, which included control variables, produced results that were highly similar in magnitude and significance to those obtained without covariates. These results confirm the robustness of our main findings, providing further evidence in support of Hypothesis 2.

Table 4. Detailed estimation results for the extended OLS Difference-in-Differences model

Variables	Periods		
	2015-2021	2016-2021	2017-2021
Treated	0.160*** (0.029)	0.236*** (0.031)	0.160*** (0.029)
Post	0.083*** (0.030)	0.083** (0.034)	0.083*** (0.030)
Treatment effect (Treated*Post)	0.183** (0.093)	0.159** (0.079)	0.145** (0.068)
Gender	-0.144*** (0.030)	-0.120*** (0.028)	-0.038 (0.025)
Age	-0.045*** (0.008)	-0.045*** (0.007)	-0.038*** (0.007)
Age squared	0.029*** (0.011)	0.025** (0.010)	0.017* (0.010)
Divorced	-0.542*** (0.052)	-0.502*** (0.051)	-0.442*** (0.052)

Variables	Periods		
	2015-2021	2016-2021	2017-2021
Widowed	-0.132 (0.083)	-0.158** (0.080)	-0.163** (0.080)
Single	-0.156*** (0.037)	-0.179*** (0.033)	-0.163*** (0.033)
Incomplete secondary	0.414*** (0.112)	0.407*** (0.118)	0.393*** (0.115)
Secondary	0.579*** (0.110)	0.571*** (0.116)	0.576*** (0.114)
Vocational	0.558*** (0.113)	0.560*** (0.119)	0.564*** (0.115)
University	0.667*** (0.114)	0.646*** (0.119)	0.661*** (0.116)
Town/Regional center	-0.398*** (0.026)	-0.373*** (0.024)	-0.314*** (0.023)
Constant	4.267*** (0.188)	4.362*** (0.180)	4.204*** (0.178)
Observations	3432	3917	4306
R-squared	0.260	0.267	0.235

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

Table 5. Estimated ATT Using SDID Method

Periods	2015-2021	2016-2021	2017-2021
Average treatment effect on treated (ATT)	0.178*** (0.058)	0.177*** (0.051)	0.177*** (0.039)
Observations	33901	33901	33901

Note: Robust standard errors in parentheses, *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1

Discussion

Our study tests two Hypotheses. The DID method could not confirm or reject Hypothesis 1, but it confirms Hypothesis 2.

Contrary to Lazareva’s (2020) study, we did not find a statistically significant adverse effect of transitioning from employment or economic inactivity to unemployment. However, we believe that the difference stems from the period under analysis. While our study estimates a short-term effect on self-reported health, Lazareva calculates the negative long-term effect of labor market shocks on health (specifically, the estimates of job loss during the 1990s on self-reported health in 2006).

Regarding re-employment in Russia, our study finds that re-employment has a positive effect on self-reported health in Russia. If we compare our findings to prior studies, we see that a study of an unemployed cohort in Rotterdam, which was conducted using a Cox proportional hazards model, concluded that obtaining a job after being unemployed was associated with improvements in both general and mental health (Schuring et al. 2011). Two articles found a positive impact of transitioning to employment on psychological health, but not on physical health. The first is a study by Gebel and Voßemer (2014) for Germany, which applied the DID to the German Socio-Economic Panel for the period 1995-2010. Similarly, a longitudinal study for Croatia for 2003-2004 provided evidence that re-employment positively impacted psychological health, while physical health was unrelated to gaining employment (Galić and Šverko 2008). Our study indicates an improvement in physical health; however, since the SRH is self-reported, we believe that individuals implicitly incorporate mental health improvements into their SRH. Our future research will measure the impact of employment transition on mental health by looking at the likelihood of depression or nervous breakdown reported by the individuals. Previous authors' calculations using an alternative quasi-randomization approach – propensity score matching – for RLMS data from 2010 to 2018 demonstrated that being employed for at least one period decreased the probability of reporting depression or nervous breakdown in the last 12 months by 4.2 percentage points (Kaneva 2024).

Our study is not without limitations. First, the reliance on self-reported health outcomes may not fully capture the comprehensive health impacts, as individuals may not be aware of their changes in physical health or new illnesses until they consult a physician. Incorporating other health metrics, such as clinical health records or stress-related biomarkers, could provide a more comprehensive understanding of health impacts. However, these health metrics were not available in the RLMS database. Second, in the traditional DID, we base our calculations on the parallel trend assumption via visualizing changes in SRH between treatment and control groups. Although this method works quite well, it would be beneficial for the study to prolong the studied periods to identify possible discrepancies in the SRH graphs between the groups. The parallel trend assumption is further relaxed in the SDID specifications, which are employed as a robustness check of the main DID results. Third, our research is done in a particular context at a specific time, so the generalizability of our findings is restricted to some extent. However, our results are in line with the scarce evidence for Europe described above. Fourth, there is evidence that fear of unemployment hinders the mental and physical health of individuals (Reichert and Tauchmann 2011). However, we are unable to measure these adverse health effects using our data and/or methodology.

Our results are robust to additional changes in the specification of the traditional model. We have altered the covariates of the extended model by substituting the variable 'town/regional center' with the variable 'resident of Moscow and St. Petersburg' for 2015-2021, 2016-2021, and 2017-2021. The results were very similar to the ones reported in Table 4. We have also changed the study period to 2010-2018 and reran the model, obtaining similar and statistically significant results. It also indicates that the period shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020-2021 and the retirement age increase since 2019 in Russia did not lead to a significant bias in the results.

Several directions of future research can improve our understanding of the studied phenomena in addition to the modeling of the impact of re-employment on mental health mentioned above. There is evidence that the impact of labor market status on health varies with the economic conditions. For instance, Brydsten et al. (2016) using DID found that

unemployed youth had significantly lower adult functional somatic symptoms during recession in Sweden (Jahlert 2009). Opposite effects – recession correlated with a negative change in health status in individuals, including the unemployed – were found for the USA. Determining which effect holds for Russia is important, as it suggests that labor and health policies should differ across the various stages of the business cycle. As was pointed out by Stuckler et al. (2009), “Active labor market programs that keep and reintegrate workers in jobs could mitigate some adverse health effects of economic downturns”.

Another promising research direction is focusing on the extended health impact of the labor market status. Marcus (2013) investigated the effect of change on the labor market status on spouses of the unemployed, applying the DID method. His research provided solid evidence that the mental health of wives diminished when their spouses were laid off due to plant closures in Germany. It means that the costs of change in labor market status are greater than previously accounted for, and, conversely, improvements in mental or physical health could be more significant in the case of re-employment of a family member. Again, this holds promise for Russia as there is a potential for decreasing health expenditure associated with re-employment that should be considered in government health and labor policies.

Conclusion and policy implications

Our research is the first for Russia to employ the quasi-experimental approach – difference-in-difference estimator – to measure the short-term causal effect of employment transition on SRH (our research was also presented in (Kaneva 2024) but it only studied one period (2010-2018))¹. By mimicking randomization, DID controls for the possible reverse causation effect and provides causal estimates of ‘treatment’ (change in the labor market status) on health indicators.

The findings of this study demonstrate that transitioning to employment has a positive impact on individual health, providing a solid basis for developing policies to increase employment opportunities and enhance working conditions, ultimately contributing to improved population health.

In Russia, considerable attention is already being paid to employment policy, aligning closely with the findings of our study. For instance, several key initiatives can be highlighted, such as the state program of the Russian Federation “Promotion of Employment of the Population” (State Program 2017), the federal project “Employment Promotion” (2024) within the national project “Demography,” and the “Digital Public Administration” (2024) initiative under the national program “Digital Economy of the Russian Federation.” The programs primarily focus on establishing and modernizing employment centers, enhancing labor mobility, providing additional professional training and skills development, creating electronic services for state employment-related support, and promoting a culture of workplace safety.

To enhance the effectiveness of employment policy in Russia, it would be advantageous to develop specialized programs that account for education levels or focus on at-risk groups – those facing significant barriers to employment, which require tailored approaches. This practice is commonly implemented in developed countries, where such groups include older adults, youth, persons with disabilities, and individuals experiencing long-term unem-

¹ For the long-term analysis, see Lazareva (2020).

ployment. Programs aimed at promoting the employment or re-employment of older adults often include initiatives such as workforce training for older individuals, financial incentives for employers (e.g., in Austria and Belgium), and earning supplements for employees to facilitate the re-entry of older workers after periods of unemployment (e.g., in Switzerland, Germany, and the UK) (Understanding the impact 2024). Another notable example is the support for youth transitioning from education to employment through dual education or professional training programs (Germany, Switzerland) (O’Higgins 2017). These innovative approaches are particularly important for the country, as they can promote better health and reduce healthcare costs in the long run by actively encouraging employment.

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Data Resources

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Ethics Statement

This study utilized publicly available data from the Russian Longitudinal Monitoring Survey (RLMS-HSE). The authors of this study had no direct involvement in data collection, and all analyses were conducted on anonymized datasets. Ethics approval was not required for this study.

Author contributions

The study was conceptualized and designed by MK, with MZ responsible for drafting the manuscript. Data analysis and the development of conclusions were conducted collaboratively by both authors.

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